

BIOcean5D

**MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND
PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL
AND HUMAN SCALES**

**D5.1 New holistic indicators of
impacts of coastal marine industries**

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List of Acronyms

AMBI - A Marine Biotic Index
ASVs - Amplicon Sequence Variants
BI - Biotic Indices
EG - Ecological Groups
EQS - Ecological Quality Status
LOOCV - Leave-One-Out-Cross-Validation
MSFD - Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NSI - Norwegian Sensitivity Index
PAH - Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
PCR - Polymerase Chain Reaction
THC - Total Hydrocarbon
TN - Total Nitrogen
TOC - Total Organic Carbon
TOM - Total Organic Matter
WGCNA - Weighted Correlation Network Analysis

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the development and assessment of new DNA-based indicators for evaluating the ecological impacts of coastal marine industries, focusing specifically on salmon aquaculture in Norway and offshore oil extraction in the North Sea. Traditional biomonitoring methods rely on morphological identification of benthic macrofauna, which is labor-intensive and dependent on expert taxonomists. In contrast, environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding offers a promising, scalable alternative for biodiversity and ecological quality status (EQS) assessments.

Using extensive datasets collected from 28 salmon aquaculture sites along the Norwegian coast and from three oil platforms in the North Sea, this report evaluates multiple strategies for inferring EQS from eDNA data. The analysis compares traditional taxonomy-based methods to three *de novo* approaches: one based on amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) and another on subcommunities of co-varying ASVs (both tested in salmon aquaculture industry) and one based on the development of a new biotic index based on DNA sequences ascribed to ecological groups (oil and gas extraction industry).

Results show that *de novo* strategies outperform taxonomy-based approaches in predicting EQS from eDNA data, with the ASV-based model achieving the highest performance. New DNA-based indicators, independent of formal taxonomic classification, were identified in both case studies. These indicators include known as well as yet unknown taxa. For instance, we identified nematodes as potential powerful bioindicators using eDNA methods in both case studies. This group was already known as comprising sensitive bioindicators from previous morphological work, but they are not yet included in routine biomonitoring programs, due to difficulty in identifying them with conventional morphology methods.

These findings provide a critical step toward integrating DNA-based methods into routine environmental monitoring of marine industries and pave the way for harmonized, cost-effective, and scalable assessments of coastal ecosystems health.

Introduction

Traditionally, the environmental impact of marine industries on seabed biodiversity is assessed by monitoring the abundance and richness of benthic macro-invertebrates. From these data, the ecological quality status (EQS) is derived to comply with the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, Directive 2008/56/EC in Europe). However, this approach is labor-intensive and requires excellent taxonomic expertise, which is scarce.

DNA-based methods have great potential to deliver such biodiversity and EQS assessments in a more timely and cost-effective manner (Taberlet et al., 2012; Pawlowski et al., 2018). Environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding, in particular, allows for high-throughput analysis of benthic communities, and proved powerful for routine biodiversity monitoring applications in both aquaculture (Lejzerowicz et al., 2015; Pawlowski et al., 2016) and oil extraction (Frontalini et al., 2020) activities. However, the implementation of DNA-based methods into routine monitoring programs is currently limited by challenges such as the need for standardized protocols (Hering et al., 2018) and comprehensive reference sequences databases (McGee et al., 2019; Weigand et al., 2019), as well as by various technical and biological biases that preclude direct comparisons with morpho-taxonomic methodologies (e.g. differences in what is considered “species” between molecular and morphological data, in relative abundances, and in community complexity).

To overcome the limitations of the taxonomy-based strategies that aim to screen known bioindicators taxa with eDNA-based methods, *de novo* strategies have been proposed (Cordier et al., 2020). Here, the aim is to combine metabarcoding data and supervised machine learning methods to identify novel bioindicators based on the distribution of metabarcodes along known impact gradients — independent of formal taxonomy — and utilize them for EQS assessment using new eDNA samples. This strategy has the advantage to expand EQS assessments to microbial (i.e. prokaryotes and protists) and meiofaunal taxa (e.g. nematodes and foraminifera) that are known to comprise powerful indicators in both aquaculture (Pawlowski et al., 2016; Stoeck et al., 2018) and offshore oil and gas extraction (Laroche et al., 2018; Pawlowski et al., 2024) industrial activities. Proof-of-concept studies showed that EQS assessments predicted using this approach were comparable to those derived from traditional macro-invertebrate surveys (Cordier et al., 2017; Cordier et al., 2018). Building upon these proof-of-concept studies, we need to upscale *de novo* strategies and assess their performance across spatial and ecological scales. To do that effectively, we need larger labeled eDNA datasets, i.e. containing both ground truth (or reference) EQS and associated eDNA data, spanning multiple ecological regions.

Here we analyse a labelled eukaryotic eDNA dataset composed of 28 locations spanning the entire coast of Norway (Figure 1) and assess the performance of two *de novo* strategies for the inference of biotic indices (BIs) used for EQS assessments in the salmon aquaculture industry (Antich et al., in prep). We also analyse a nematodes eDNA dataset collected along pressures gradient near three oil platforms in the North Sea (Pawlowski et al., 2024; Frontalini et al., 2025), to assess the performance of nematodes eDNA data for impact assessments of the offshore oil extraction industry. For both of these datasets, we identified new DNA-based bioindicators that could be further developed and leveraged by future benthic monitoring programs to be implemented for marine industries.

1. Salmon aquaculture industry

1.1. Material and methods

1.1.1. Sampling and morphology-based biotic indices.

Sediment samples were collected from 2015 to 2019 in 28 aquaculture locations spanning the Norwegian coast (Figure 1). These locations encompass a total of 142 sampling stations, with each locality having between three and seven sampling stations. At each station, up to two Van Veen grab casts were done. The sampling locations were positioned along theoretical pressure gradients, ranging from directly beneath salmon cages (0 m, indicating potential impact) to a maximum of ca. 1,000 m away (indicating minimal impact, serving as a reference station). For each grab at a given station, two to three sediment replicates (5-10 g) were collected using sterile plastic spoons for DNA extraction. The remaining sediment from each grab was sieved onboard, and the recovered macrofaunal specimens were stored in formaldehyde. These specimens were then prepared for routine taxonomic analyses as part of the biomonitoring program conducted by environmental consultancy companies. From this morpho-taxonomic data, we used the BBI R package (Cordier & Pawlowski, 2018) to calculate the AMBI (Borja et al., 2000) and NSI (Rygg & Norling, 2013) indices that are commonly used for benthic monitoring in the salmon aquaculture industry in Norway.

Figure 1. Sampling locations of the 28 salmon farms sampled and analysed in this study.

1.1.2. DNA metabarcoding data

The V1V2 region of the 18S ribosomal RNA gene was amplified using Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) with the primers F04mod (5'-GCTTGWCTCAAAGATTAAGCC-3') and

R22mod (5'-CCTGCTGCCTTCCTTGA-3') over 35 cycles (95 °C for 30 s, 57 °C for 45 s, 72 °C for 1 min and 72 °C for 2 min). Unique combinations of tag-encoded versions of the primers (8-nucleotide long) were used to multiplex up to 35 samples into single sequencing libraries. PCR products were quantified using high-resolution capillary electrophoresis (QIAxcel System, Qiagen) and pooled in equimolar concentrations for each library. We purified each pool using the High Pure PCR Product Purification Kit (Roche) and quantified them using a fluorometric method (QuBit HS dsDNA kit, Invitrogen). Library preparation was performed using the TruSeq DNA PCR-Free Library Prep Kit (Illumina), followed by quantification with the KAPA qPCR kit to load equimolar libraries onto an Illumina MiSeq sequencing instrument.

1.1.3. Bioinformatics

Raw sequencing data was processed using the SLIM web application v0.6.2 (Dufresne et al., 2019). The module “demultiplexer” was used for demultiplexing of the library files into separate pairs of fastq files for each sample (trim_end = true; trim_length = 1; mistags = false; errors = 0. Module “DADA2” (by_lib = true; pool = false), which is based on the DADA2 v1.16 pipeline (Callahan et al., 2016), was used for inference of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) and chimera detection to obtain an ASV-to-sample matrix. For the taxonomic assignment of ASVs, the module “assignment-table-vsearch” was used (similarity = 0.9; acceptance = 0.99; cons_num = 3). This module uses vsearch v2.8.0 (Rognes et al., 2016) to assign a taxonomic name to each ASV with the usearch_global algorithm. If there are more than one “best match” above the set similarity cutoff, their taxonomy is compared and the consensus taxonomic rank across these is used for the query sequence. We assigned the taxonomy to our ASVs using the PR2 v5.0.0 reference database (Guillou et al., 2013). We discarded samples that had less than 10,000 reads, as well as ASVs occurring in less than 1% of the total number of samples across the entire dataset. Then, we applied the Hellinger transformation of reads counts (i.e. the square root of the relative abundances) to account for variations in sequencing depth.

1.1.4. Statistics

We used the vegan R package (Oksanen et al., 2018) to analyse both alpha (richness and diversity) and beta (community composition) diversity patterns from the metabarcoding data. We then performed a clustering analysis of the samples to identify a potential biogeographical structure along the Norwegian coast. Then, we compared the performance of three different strategies to infer the AMBI and NSI biotic indices values from metabarcoding data: a) taxonomy-based, i.e. relying on the relative abundances of ASV assigned to known macrofaunal bioindicator taxa; b) *de novo* ASV, i.e. calibrating a supervised machine learning model and predicting AMBI and NSI values from the ASV composition regardless from their taxonomic affiliation; and c) *de novo* subcommunities, i.e. calibrating a supervised machine learning model and predicting AMBI and NSI values from groups (or modules) of co-varying ASVs across the dataset. We measured the performance of random forest (RF) regressions in predicting the BI values from the ASVs composition profiles by using a Leave-One-Out-Cross-Validation (LOOCV) strategy at the locality level, i.e. all the samples of a given locality were held-out (i.e. the test set) and used to predict the BI from their ASV composition with the RF regression model trained on the rest of the data (i.e. the training set). This process was repeated for the 28 localities available in our entire dataset, i.e. the BI values of all samples of a given locality were predicted independently

once, based on a model trained on all the samples from all other localities. To compare the performance of our three different inference strategies, we assessed the correlation between observed and predicted BI continuous values using an anova, as well as multiple classification performance metrics from discrete EQS derived from the AMBI and NSI values. Such metrics included the accuracy (ratio of correctly predicted to the total number of observations), the precision (ratio of correctly predicted to the total predicted) and the recall (ratio of correctly predicted to all the observations in the actual class) for each EQS derived from the BI values. We then used the weighted total precision and recall (this is the sum of each metric multiplied by the proportion of samples of each class) to calculate the F1-score as a measure of balance between these two metrics. We also explored how the sampling effort (i.e. the size of the training dataset) impacts the performance of the random forest supervised machine learning models in predicting the AMBI and NSI BI values. Finally, we searched for new DNA-based bioindicators, by scrutinizing groups of co-varying ASVs (i.e. modules) that respond to aquaculture impacts in a similar manner across the different aquaculture sites, and that are not associated to any given biogeographic region. These were considered as new DNA-based bioindicators that could be further developed and validated.

1.2. Results

1.1.5. Morphology-based data

A total of 257,931 macrofauna specimens, representing 925 taxa, 649 of them with species name, across a total 273 grabs were extracted from the routine, morphology-based biomonitoring reports produced by consultancy companies (Figure 2). For the stations sampled right beneath the cages, the relative abundance of Annelida was almost 100% (with 76% of *Capitella* sp., a common bioindicator taxa of aquaculture impacts), except for the Lyngvaer locality. Mollusca relative abundances increased as a function of increasing distance from the cages. AMBI values ranged from 0.43 (i.e. high EQS) to 6 (i.e. poor EQS) and NSI values ranged from 4.68 (i.e. poor EQS) to 26.69 (i.e. high EQS). Both BI values showed a consistent and steady decrease in the impact of salmon aquaculture as the distance from the cages increases (Figure 3).

1.1.6. Metabarcoding data

We obtained sequencing data for a total of 711 DNA samples from sediments collected in 138 stations in 28 localities along the Norwegian coast. Two of these stations were discarded after filtering samples with less than 10,000 reads. Thus, we analysed 685 samples (mean of $79,239 \pm 1,879$ reads per sample) from 136 stations. The quality-filtered metabarcoding data was composed of a total of 54,278,908 DNA reads (2.65 % reads were filtered from the raw data) representing 3,395 ASVs assigned to 918 different taxa, 423 of them at the species level. ASVs identified as Metazoans represented 43.01% of the reads and their taxonomy profile showed that Annelida were abundant across all localities, whereas Arthropoda and Nematoda showed higher relative abundances than for morphology-based data (Figure 2). Reads assigned to non-Metazoans taxa were mostly assigned to Stramenopiles and followed by Alveolata and Rhizaria leaving the rest of the groups and those unidentified ASVs to less than 18 % of the reads in all stations. Compared to morphology-based taxonomic profiles, metabarcoding analysis detected more phyla and a higher diversity at higher taxonomic ranks. However, we found no consistent pattern across localities along the distance gradients from the cage.

Figure 2. Taxonomic structure of metazoans communities in the sampled stations of all localities using both metabarcoding (left) and morphology (right) analysis. The 10 most abundant groups are shown, and the rest are grouped in "Others". Colors of the localities represent the different clusters obtained from the beta diversity analysis of the control stations (C1, black; C2, ocre; C3, salmon; C4, cyan; C5, brown; see figure 4). Each bar

represents a station and in each locality these are ordered from closer to the cage (up) to farther (down).

Figure 3: AMBI and NSI values along the distance from the fish farm cages obtained from the analysis of the morphological data.

1.1.7. Biogeographic structure and community profiles

Our cluster analysis revealed five different clusters (or ecological regions) (Figure 4), somewhat distributed along a North to South transect: one highly connected between localities (i.e. with homogeneous community profiles in their reference stations relative to other biogeographic regions) in the north (Cluster 1, C1); a more patched distributed geographically in the south (Cluster 2, C2); and three smaller clusters, of one (Cluster 3, C3) and two localities (Clusters 4 and 5, C4, C5), between the latitudes of the southern cluster. The C5 comprised localities that were most dissimilar to the other localities in the dataset.

Figure 4. Biogeographic analysis of the 28 aquaculture localities, revealing five clusters or “eco-regions”.

The distribution of the samples on the two dimensions of the NMDS ordination was consistent with the detected biogeographic structure, with samples from the same cluster tending to group together (Figure 5). Latitude was the main vector correlated with the distribution of samples on the ordination ($R^2=0.69$, $p < 0.001$) followed perpendicularly by the Shannon diversity ($R^2=0.66$, $p < 0.001$). NSI, distance from the cage and AMBI, were also perpendicular to the Latitude vector but these were less correlated with samples distribution on the NMDS ($R^2=0.09$, 0.06 & 0.06 respectively; all with $p < 0.001$).

Figure 5. NMDS ordination of samples as a function of identified biogeographic structure (top left), Ecological Quality Status (EQS) based on AMBI (bottom left) and NSI (bottom right). Lines (top right) represent the environmental variables fitted to the ordination using the envfit function of the vegan R package.

We decomposed the multivariate variance (i.e. variance in community composition) due to biogeography and aquaculture impact using permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) models. Biogeography explained 21% of total variance, while the aquaculture impact, as measured by AMBI and NSI values, explained about 5%.

1.1.8. Performance of BI and EQS predictions

Taxonomy-based strategy.

We compared the AMBI and NSI values obtained from metabarcoding data with the ones obtained from conventional morphological analysis of macrofauna. A total of 193 taxonomically annotated ASVs were found in the BBI reference database for the AMBI index, whereas 77 ASVs were found in the BBI database for NSI. Compared to morphology approaches, where 811 taxa matched an entry in the BBI database for AMBI (465 for NSI), our results show that DNA-based methods, at this level of sampling effort, recover less than half of the bioindicator taxa detected via conventional morphological approaches. Correlation between inferred and reference BI values was positive for both AMBI ($R^2=0.55$, $p < 0.001$) for AMBI, and NSI ($R^2=0.37$, $p < 0.001$, fig. 7A) for NSI, $p < 0.001$ for both, Figure 6A).

ASV-based de novo strategy.

We measured the performance of random forest (RF) regressions in predicting the BI values from the ASVs composition profiles by cross validation. The correlation analysis between predicted and reference BI values showed similar results for both AMBI ($R^2=0.73$ and $p < 0.001$) and NSI ($R^2=0.7$ and $p < 0.001$; Figure 6B). Using RF models thus improved the predictive performance compared to the taxonomy-based strategy, especially for the NSI index. Although the differences in R^2 were low between taxonomy-based and RF-based strategy for AMBI, the discrete classification of these BI values into EQS showed that the performance was improved (from 55 to 61.6% of correct EQS inference for AMBI, and from 37.7 to 52.2% for NSI).

Subcommunities-based de novo strategy.

Our results show that the predictions were again better for both AMBI and NSI compared to a taxonomy-based approach. This is shown in the higher correlation value ($R^2=0.68$ for AMBI and $R^2=0.66$ for NSI, Figure 6C). However, the performance was slightly lower here compared to the ASV-based strategy. A similar trend was observed with the proportion of well predicted discrete EQS.

Figure 6: AMBI (top) and NSI (bottom) predictive performance for the three tested strategies: A) Calculated BIs values using a taxonomy-based approach where only taxonomically annotated ASVs are used as input in the BBI package; B) Predicted BIs values using the random forest algorithm trained on ASVs composition profiles; and C) Predicted BIs values using subcommunities eigenvalues (i.e. the first principal component). Colors of dots represent the different biogeographic clusters obtained from the beta diversity analysis of the control stations (see Figure 4). The colored boxes represent the five discrete classes of EQS (from “poor” in red to “high” in blue).

Classification metrics.

The classification performance metrics showed the same pattern described above (Figure 7). The F1-score shows that the taxonomy-based strategy gives the lowest performance, whereas the ASV-based *de novo* strategy delivers the best EQS assessments.

Figure 7: Bar plot of the precision (left), recall (center) and F1 (right) as function of the Ecological Quality Status (EQS) based on AMBI (top) and NSI (bottom) for the three strategies tested to predict the EQS: BBI package (black), Random Forest (RF) with all ASVs (grey) and RF with all modules obtained from the WGCNA analysis (light grey).

Effect of training set size on performance.

Investigating the effect of training set size showed that predictive performance reaches a plateau at 5-10 sampled sites (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Root Mean Square Error (i.e. lower means better) as function of increasing the number of localities in the training set for RF models to predict the AMBI (top) and NSI (bottom) values for both ASV (left) and subcommunities (right) datasets for the different clusters obtained in the biogeography analysis (see Figure 4).

1.3. New DNA-based indicators of impact

We analyzed how each group of co-varying ASVs (i.e. "modules") were related to aquaculture impact, and how these were linked to biogeography. Each module is referred to by a color name, based on the WGCNA analysis. We identified certain modules that contain new DNA-based indicators of aquaculture impact and that are not linked to any specific region. This suggests they respond similarly to aquaculture across the Norwegian coast (Figure 9). Six such modules were found to comprise new DNA-based indicators of aquaculture impact, "Green" module is linked to High EQS, "SteelBlue" module is linked to Moderate EQS, "Pink" module is linked to Bad EQS, "Lightyellow", "Yellowgreen", and "Sienna3" modules are linked to Poor EQS.

Figure 9: Tile plot showing for each module of ASVs their association with aquaculture impact (EQS High, Moderate, Bad and Poor) as well as with the biogeography (Cluster C1, C2, C3 & C4). Modules associated with a given EQS and not with biogeography were considered as comprising potential new DNA-based indicators (in red on the plot).

Among them, the “Green” module was rich in Filosa-Thecofilosea and Dinophyceae ASVs. These taxa are likely planktonic, which could indicate that when aquaculture impact is low (high EQS), plankton taxa are more likely to be detected in the sediment. The “Yellowgreen” module (associated with Poor EQS) was mostly made up of parasitic Syndiniales, making up about 80% of its ASVs (Figure 10). “Pink” (associated with bad EQS) and “Steelblue” (associated with moderate EQS) modules were composed mostly of nematode ASVs.

Figure 10: Tile plot showing the relative abundance of taxonomic groups within the modules identified as compising new DNA-based indicators of aquaculture. ASVs within modules were grouped by taxonomic ranks for visualization purposes. The EQS to which the module is associated is indicated on the top.

1.4. Outlook

Our results show that *de novo* strategies are a powerful alternative to taxonomy-based strategies for the routine monitoring of coastal marine ecosystems using eDNA methods. Even in the presence of a pronounced biogeographic structure, machine learning models delivered BI values and EQS assessments that are closer to the ground-truth morphology-based EQS assessments (Figure 6-7). We identified new DNA-based bioindicators that are spatially robust, and independent from formal taxonomy (Figure 10). These strategies therefore allow bypassing the limitations of taxonomy-based eDNA methods to infer EQS, because they are not affected by the incompleteness of reference DNA sequence databases used for taxonomic annotations of eDNA data. Even though we strongly advocate for sustaining efforts to fill these reference DNA sequence databases to improve taxonomic annotations of environmental DNA sequences, we also argue that eDNA-based methods can readily be combined with *de novo* strategies for the routine biomonitoring of aquaculture impacts in coastal Norway.

2. Oil and gas extraction industry

2.1. Material and methods

2.1.1. Sampling design and environmental data

In summer 2021, surface sediment samples were collected near three offshore oil and gas platforms – DANF, TYRA, and GORM – operated by TotalEnergies in the North Sea, about 180 km from Denmark’s west coast (Figure 11). Samples were taken along four distance gradients from each platform (100 m, 250 m, 750 m, 1500 m, and 3000 m), plus two reference sites located over 10 km away from any platform. Around DANF, 20 stations were sampled, while TYRA and GORM each had 18. An additional 22 samples from DANF, collected in May 2018, were also analyzed. At each station, sediment cores were taken with a Haps sediment corer, and subsamples from the top, 5 cm, and 10 cm depths were combined. Samples were frozen at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until DNA was extracted. Three samples per station were used for eDNA analysis and metabarcoding, totaling 252 samples.

Figure 11: Map of the sampled oil platforms in the North Sea showing the location of Dan F, Gorm and Tyra platforms and reference stations

2.1.2. DNA metabarcoding data

Environmental DNA (eDNA) was extracted using the DNeasy Power Max Soil kit (Qiagen). About 10 g of sediment was processed following the kit instructions, and DNA was stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until PCR. Two genetic markers from the 18S rRNA gene were targeted: V1V2 (modified for nematodes) and V9 (a general eukaryotic marker). The V1V2-Nema primers were specifically optimized for nematodes by adjusting the forward and reverse sequences (Pawlowski et al., 2024), while V9 primers are commonly used for broad eukaryotic surveys (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2009). The amplified fragments were $\sim 300\text{--}400$ bp for V1V2-Nema

and ~120–150 bp for V9. All primers were tagged with 8-base barcodes for sample multiplexing during sequencing. PCR was done in triplicate for each DNA sample using 1 μ L of template in a 25 μ L reaction. The V1V2-Nema PCR followed a cycling program with 35 cycles at 95 °C (30 s), 59 °C (30 s), and 72 °C (1 min), with final denaturation and elongation steps. PCR conditions for V9 followed a cycling program initial denaturation step at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 s, annealing at 57°C for 1 min, extension at 72°C for 1.5 min, and a final extension at 72°C for 2 min. Negative controls were included to check for potential contaminations. Triplicate PCRs were pooled and quantified with QIAxcel (Qiagen). Equal amounts of PCR products were cleaned and combined, and libraries were prepared using the Illumina TruSeq® PCR-Free kit. Final quantification was done by qPCR, and sequencing was carried out on an Illumina MiSeq platform.

2.1.3. Bioinformatics

Raw sequencing data was processed with the SLIM application (Dufresne et al., 2019) using the DADA2 workflow (Callahan et al., 2016). This included removing low-quality reads, identifying Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs), and filtering out chimeras – all using default settings. ASVs were assigned a taxonomy using the VSEARCH module in SLIM. For V9 data, the PR2 v4.12 database was used, while SILVA v138 was used for V1V2-Nema. ASVs were annotated based on up to three best matches in the reference database, requiring at least 85% similarity for V9 and 90% for V1V2-Nema. Matches above 99% were directly assigned to that reference. Any V9 ASVs identified as prokaryotic were excluded. For V1V2-Nema, we first calculated the proportion of nematode reads per sample to check primer specificity, then removed all non-nematode ASVs before continuing. The final ASV tables were then analyzed using the R statistical software (R Core Team, 2016).

2.1.4. Statistics

We first compared the beta diversity patterns between the 18S V9 eukaryotes marker and the nematodes-focused V1V2 marker, using the vegan R package. We normalized ASV tables using cumulative sum scaling (CSS) and calculated Bray-Curtis pairwise distances. These distances were used for non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) with grouping by distance classes and sampling year. We also ran ANOSIM tests to compare communities across platforms and years. We also examined how environmental variables correlated with NMDS results. We then attempted to build a new biotic index based on nematode metabarcoding data (V1V2-Nema), called nema-gAMBI, by ascribing nematode ASVs into discrete ecological groups. We performed a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on environmental variables, including trace elements, organic matter (TOM, TOC, TOC/TN), and pollutants (THC, PAHs). From this, we extracted a pollution gradient and correlated it with the relative abundance of nematode ASVs using Spearman's correlation (ρ coefficient). Based on correlation strength, ASVs were grouped into five ecological groups (EGs), i.e. sensitive (ρ -1 to -0.4, EGI), indifferent (ρ -0.4 to 0.4, EGII), tolerant (ρ 0.4 to 0.5, EGIII), second-order opportunistic (ρ 0.5 to 0.6, EGIV) and opportunistic (ρ 0.6 to 1, EGV). These groupings were used to calculate the nema-gAMBI index for each sample following the following formula: $(0 \times \text{EGI}\%) + (1.5 \times \text{EGII}\%) + (3 \times \text{EGIII}\%) + (4.5 \times \text{EGIV}\%) + (6 \times \text{EGV}\%) \times 100$. The nema-gAMBI values were then averaged per station and compared with the traditional macrofaunal-based AMBI values.

2.2. Results

2.2.1. Metabarcoding data

After quality filtering, we retained about 24 million reads for the V9 marker and 12 million for the V1V2-Nema marker. In the V9 dataset, 569 prokaryotic ASVs (1.3% of reads) were removed. For V1V2-Nema, 8816 non-nematode ASVs (31.3% of reads) were discarded. The final number of ASVs kept per platform ranged from 5911 to 10,323 for V9, and 2267 to 2843 for V1V2-Nema.

2.2.2. Taxonomic structure

The V9 dataset covered a broad range of eukaryotic groups. It also picked up some bacteria, but they made up only a small portion of the data (1.3% of reads, 3% of ASVs). The V9 dataset was mainly composed of metazoans (41% of reads), followed by Stramenopiles (24%), Cercozoa (9%), and unassigned sequences (8%). Other notable groups included Ciliophora and Dinoflagellata (6% each). Among metazoans, the most common were arthropods (mainly copepods), annelids, and nematodes, along with noticeable proportions of platyhelminths, nemertean, and echinoderms. Overall, the taxonomic makeup was fairly consistent across platforms (Figure 12), but some site-specific differences were observed. For example, metazoans were more dominant in DANF21 compared to DANF18, which had more alveolates and Cercozoa. Echinoderms were more prominent at TYRA, but less so at GORM and both DANF sites.

Figure 12: Taxonomic structure (relative abundances) of the V9 dataset for each oil platform.

The V1V2-Nema marker is a modified version of the V1V2 region, specifically designed to target marine nematodes. The proportion of nematode reads varied across platforms—from an average of 62.7% at TYRA to 78.8% at DANF21, reaching up to 90% in some DANF samples (Figure 13). Besides nematodes, the dataset included a small number of other eukaryotes, mainly Cercozoa (9%) and Stramenopiles (8%), with other groups each below 3% (Fig. 3). The overall taxonomic makeup differed slightly between platforms (Figure 13), mostly due to changes in nematode abundance—lower at TYRA, where other eukaryotes were more prominent.

Figure 13: Proportion of nematodes reads in the V1V2-Nema dataset for each oil platform.

In terms of nematodes families, Cyatholaimidae dominated at both DANF sites, Comesomatidae at GORM, and Chromadoridae at TYRA (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Taxonomic structure (relative abundances) of the V1V2-Nema dataset for each oil platform.

2.2.3. Beta diversity patterns

We examined how community composition changed along distance gradients from the platforms, using both the V9 and V1V2-Nema datasets. First, we looked at all four platforms together. The two markers revealed different patterns. In the V9 dataset, DANF18 and DANF21 formed clear, separate clusters, while GORM and TYRA overlapped more (figure 15A). In contrast, the V1V2-Nema dataset showed a large overlap between DANF18 and DANF21, but GORM and TYRA stayed relatively distinct (figure 15B). These patterns were supported by ANOSIM results (figures 15C and 15D), which showed low differentiation between DANF18 and DANF21 in the V1V2-Nema data, but stronger differences between the other platform pairs. This means that nematode communities are more stable through time than when considering the whole eukaryotic communities.

Figure 15: Non-metric multidimensional scaling ordinations based on Bray-Curtis distance matrices for both V9 (A) and V1V2-Nema datasets (B). ANOSIM analysis of community differentiation for V9 (C) and V1V2-Nema datasets (D). ANOSIM statistic (i. e., community differentiation) and permutation-based p values results are indicated (***: p -value < 0.001)

2.3. New DNA-based indicators of impact

Figure 16: Principal Component Analysis of environmental variables. Color scale indicates strength of contribution of variables to the ordination.

The first axis of the PCA is related to most trace elements, THC, PAHs, and organic matter (i.e., TOM, TOC, TP and TN) and has been, therefore, interpreted as the 'pollution gradient' (Figure 16).

Then we correlated our nematodes ASVs to this pollution gradients ASVs Spearman's rank correlation. Out of the 2251 nematodes ASVs, we ascribed 278 ASVs into discrete ecological groups nema-gAMBI (14 as opportunistic, 43 as second-order opportunistic, 158 as sensitive, and 63 as tolerant taxa, see a selection in table 1).

Using these indicators ASVs, we calculated nema-gAMBI for all the samples and compared them with conventional macrofauna-based AMBI index values (Figure 17). This showed strong correlation with the traditional AMBI ($\rho = 0.74$), indicating good agreement between the two indices. Cohen's Kappa ($\kappa = 0.62$) confirmed substantial consistency in how both methods assessed EQS around the oil platforms.

Table 1: Selection of most abundant new DNA-based indicator ASVs for assessing EQS around oil platforms, their ecological group, their taxonomic annotation, and their similarity with reference sequences. ASV sequences are available in the annex.

ASV_ID	Rho	Ecological group	Taxon	Similarity
ASV1	0,66	Opportunistic	Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus	91,7
ASV28	0,67	Opportunistic	Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Leptonemella aphanothecae	98,3
ASV37	0,65	Opportunistic	Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus	92,7
ASV43	0,65	Opportunistic	Desmodorida;Epsilonematidae ;Perepsilonema corsicum	96,5
ASV53	0,66	Opportunistic	Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria armata	99
ASV57	0,67	Opportunistic	Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus	91,1
ASV60	0,61	Opportunistic	Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus	91,4
ASV72	0,66	Opportunistic	Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria pulchra	94,7
ASV11	0,58	SO opportunistic	Enoplida;Thoracostomopsidae;Mesacanthion ungulatum	94,5
ASV24	0,52	SO opportunistic	Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria armata	99,7
ASV33	0,57	SO opportunistic	Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Neochromadora sp.	97,7
ASV36	0,55	SO opportunistic	Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Spirinia parasitifera	99
ASV51	0,5	SO opportunistic	Araeolaimida sp.	90,1
ASV62	0,54	SO opportunistic	Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria armata	99,3
ASV64	0,58	SO opportunistic	Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus	92,4
ASV10	-0,64	Sensitive	unassigned	
ASV16	-0,6	Sensitive	unassigned	
ASV17	-0,65	Sensitive	Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Rhips paraornata	94,1
ASV18	-0,54	Sensitive	unassigned	
ASV20	-0,57	Sensitive	Enoplida;Thoracostomopsidae;Enoploides sp.	98,3
ASV21	-0,7	Sensitive	Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Chromadorita tentabundum	98,9
ASV23	-0,53	Sensitive	Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Neochromadora sp.	99
ASV32	-0,72	Sensitive	Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Desmodora pontica	100
ASV35	-0,6	Sensitive	Desmodorida;Monoposthiidae;Monoposthia mirabilis	100
ASV40	-0,7	Sensitive	Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Prochromadorella antarctica	99
ASV44	-0,44	Sensitive	unassigned	
ASV54	-0,43	Sensitive	Desmodorida;Microlaimidae;Calomicrolaimus parahonestus	98
ASV2	0,46	Tolerant	Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria punctata	99

ASV4	0,49	Tolerant	unassigned	
ASV7	0,41	Tolerant	Enoplida;Thoracostomopsidae;Enoploides sp.	98
ASV12	0,41	Tolerant	Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Metachromadora remanei	96
ASV70	0,44	Tolerant	Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus	92,1
ASV75	0,41	Tolerant	Monhysterida;Xyalidae;Daptonema oxycerca	91,7
ASV76	0,41	Tolerant	unassigned	

Figure 17: Scatter plots of AMBI and nema-gAMBI values obtained for the three oil platforms. Spearman rho is 0.74.

2.4. Outlook

Our results show that it is possible to target nematodes with eDNA methods for the detection of impacts in three oil and gas extraction platforms in the North Sea. We developed a new biotic index, nema-gAMBI, based on the distribution of nematodes metabarcodes along impact gradients. The AMBI values obtained by using the nema-gAMBI index and the traditional morphology data were similar (Figure 17). We identified nematodes bioindicators taxa (Table 1) that are used by the nema-gAMBI for EQS assessments. However, this proof-of-concept study is based on a limited number of independent sites, and within the same geographical region. We advocate expanding the spatial scale of the nema-gAMBI, in order to test for its broad applicability.

Conclusion

This study provides evidence that eDNA metabarcoding, combined with advanced statistical and machine learning techniques, can significantly enhance the detection and monitoring of ecological impacts from marine industries. Across two case studies—salmon aquaculture along the Norwegian coast and offshore oil and gas extraction in the North Sea—we identified new DNA-based bioindicators, independent of formal taxonomy, that allow developing monitoring strategies producing accurate ecological quality status assessments. DNA-based biomonitoring strategies, especially *de novo*, represent a step-change in terms of scalability and breadth of surveyed biodiversity. This opens the way for an expanded and more timely management of coastal marine ecosystems.

Key results include:

- In the salmon *aquaculture sector*, six groups of co-varying ASVs (i.e. called modules or subcommunities) were identified as comprising powerful new indicators. These modules were associated with specific EQS levels, irrespective of geographic location. Taxonomically, they included ASVs from diverse groups such as Filosa-Thecofilosea and Dinophyceae (linked to high EQS), Syndiniales (linked to poor EQS), and various nematodes (linked to moderate and bad EQS).
- In the *oil and gas extraction sector*, a nematode-specific biotic index (nema-gAMBI) was successfully developed. It is based on 278 nematode ASVs that were ascribed to ecological groups based on their correlation with measured pollution gradients. Several species, including *Praeacanthonus punctatus*, *Sabatieria armata*, and *Desmodora pontica*, emerged as key indicators. The nema-gAMBI index correlated well with conventional AMBI and achieved substantial agreement in EQS classification.

These findings underscore the potential of combining eDNA analysis with *de novo* strategies to identify new DNA-based bioindicators, including previously overlooked microbial and meiofaunal taxa. This approach expands the taxonomic scope of biomonitoring programs and enables more comprehensive and cost-effective assessments, contributing to a better and timely management of coastal ecosystems.

Future Perspectives

Building on this work, future efforts should focus on:

- Expanding reference datasets (containing both ground truth EQS and eDNA data), to better control for natural variations in community composition due to biogeography.
- Validating new DNA-based bioindicators across broader spatial and temporal scales, including different oceanographic regions and possibly additional marine industries (e.g., wind farms, dredging, seafloor mining).
- Integrating new DNA-based bioindicators into national and international monitoring frameworks, such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC).

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Annex 1

Selection of Nematodes ASVs identified as bioindicators index of impacts around three oil platforms in the North Sea and included in the nema-gAMBI (Frontalini et al., 2025).

ASV1|Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus|Opportunistic
TCTAAGCACAAGCCAAAAACGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTT
ATTGGATCTTCCTCTATACATGGATACCTGCAGTAATTCTGGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAG
CTCCAACCTTACGGACGGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTAG
TTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGT
AA

ASV28|Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Leptonemella aphanothecae|Opportunistic
TCTAAGCATGAGCCGAATTATGGTGAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTTGTTT
CTTGGATCTTACTTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCAACTCAGC
TCCAACCTTACGGAAGGAGCGCATTATTATACCAAACCAATCAGGCTTGCCCTGTAGTT
TGGTGACTCTGAATAACTATGCTGATCACAAGGTCCTAGTACCGGTGACATATCTTTCAA
GTGTCTGCCCTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTCGTAACGGGTAA

ASV37|Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus|Opportunistic
TCTAAGCATAAGCCGAAAAACGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTT
ATTGGATCTTCCTCTATACATGGATACCTGCAGTAATTCTGGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAG
CTCCAACCTTACGGGCGGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTAG
TTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGT
AA

ASV43|Desmodorida;Epsilonematidae ;Perepsilonema corsicum|Opportunistic
TCTAAGCATGAGCCGAATTATGGTGAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTTGTTT
CTTGGATCTTAATTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCAACCAAGCT
CCAACCTTTCGGAAGGAGCGCATTATTATACCAAGACCAATCGGGCTTTGCCCGCTATC
TGGTGACTCTGAATAACTTTGCTGATCACATGGTCATAGTACCGGTGACATATCTTTCAAG
TGTCTGCCCTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTAA

ASV53|Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria armata |Opportunistic
TCTAAGCAGAAGCCGCACAACGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTCGTT
TCTTGGATCTCTAATTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCACTAAA
GCTCCGACCTTACGGGACGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGTTTCGGCCCG
TCCGTTGGTGACTCTGAATAACTACGCCGATCGCACGGTCTCGTACCGGCGACATATCT
TTCAAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGG
GTAA

ASV57|Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus|Opportunistic

TCTAAGCACAAGCCAAAAACGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTT
 ATTGGATCTTCTCTATACATGGATACCTGCAGTAATTCTGGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAG
 CTCCAACCTTACGGACGGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTAG
 TTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTTC
 AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
 A

ASV60|Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus|Opportunistic
 TCTAAGCACAAGCCAAAAACGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATACTTT
 ATTGGATCTTCTCTATACATGGATACCTGCAGTAATTCTGGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAG
 CTCCAACCTTACGGACGGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTAG
 TTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTTC
 AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGT
 AA

ASV72|Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria pulchra |Opportunistic
 TCTAAGCAGAAGCCGCACAACGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTCGTT
 TCTTGGATCTCTAATTTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCACTAAA
 GCTCCGACCTTACGGGACGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTA
 GTTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTT
 CAAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGG
 TAA

ASV11|Enoplida;Thoracostomopsidae;Mesacanthion ungulatum|SO opportunistic
 TCTCAGTACATTCCGATAAATGGAGAAACCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTTA
 TTAGATCTTACTCTACTTGGATACCTGTGGTAACCTAAGAGCTAATACATGCAACTAAGTC
 CTGACTTTACGGGAAGGACGCATTATTAGAAATAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGCTCTTT
 GGTGAATCTGAATAACTATGCCGATCGCACAGTCCTCGTACTGGCGACGTATCTTTCAA
 TGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGACGGTAGTTTACACGGCTACCGTGGTTTTTCACGGGTAA

ASV24|Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria armata|SO opportunistic
 TCTAAGCAGAAGCCGCACAACGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTCGTT
 TCTTGGATCTCTAATTTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCACTAAA
 GCTCCGACCTTACGGGACGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGTTTCAGCCCG
 TTCGTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTAAGCCGATCGCACGGTCTCGTACCGGCGACGTATCT
 TTCAAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGG
 GTAA

ASV33|Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Neochromadora sp.|SO opportunistic
 TCTAAGCATAAACCGAATATGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTTAT
 TGGATCTTAGAGTCCTACTTGGATACCTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCAATCAAG
 CCCCACCTTACGGGCGGGGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATTGGCTTCGGCCATAG
 ATTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCTGATCGCACGGCTTGTCCCGGCGACGTATCCTTC
 AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
 A

ASV36|Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Spirinia parasitifera|SO opportunistic
 TCTAAGCATGAGCCGAATAATGGTGAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTTGTTT
 CTTGGATCTTGATTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGTGAAAAAGC
 TCCAACCTTACGGAAGGAGCGCATTATTAGACCAAGACCAATCAGGCTTTGCCTGTAAT
 CTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTTTGCTGATCACATGGTCTAGCACCGGTGACATATCTTTC
 AGTGTCTGCCCTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
 A

ASV51|Araeolaimida sp.|SO opportunistic

TCTCAGCACAAAGCCAAAACAAGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCAATATAACAGTCATTGTTT
ACTGGATCTTAACCATCCTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCAAAA
AGCTCTGACCTTCTGGAATGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATGGGGCTTGCCCTA
ACTGGTGGATCTAAGTAACCTCAGCTGATCGCACGACCTCGTGTGCGGCGACGTATCTTCC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTATGATGGTAGTTTATGCGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
A

ASV62|Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria armata|SO opportunistic

TCTAAGCAGAAGCCGAACAACGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTCGTT
TCTTGGATCTCTTATTTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCACTAAA
GCTCCGACCTTACGGGACGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGTTTCGGCCCG
TTCGTTGGTGACTCTGAATAACTAAGCCGATCGCACGGTCTCGTACCGGCGACGTATCT
TTCAAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGG
GTAA

ASV64|Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonchus punctatus|SO opportunistic

TCTAAGCATAAGCCGAAAAACGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTT
ATTGGATCTTCCTCTATACATGGATACCTGCAGTAATTCTGGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAG
CTCCAACCTTACGGACGGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTAG
TTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGT
AA

ASV10|unassigned|Sensitive

TCTAAGTATAAGCATTACTACTGTGAAACTGCGAATGGCTCATTATATCAGTTATAGTTTATT
TGATAGTACCTTACTACTTGGATAACCGTAGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCACCAAGTC
CCGACTGCCTGTGCGGAAGGGATGTCTTTATTAGATCGAAACCAATGCAGGGGGCAACCC
TGGTATTGTGGTGATTATAATAACTGTGCGAATCGCATGGCCCCGTGCCGGCGATAAAT
CATTCAAGTTTCTGCCCTATCAGCTTTCGATGGTAGGGTATTGGCCTACCATGGCGTTAA
CGGGTAA

ASV16|unassigned|Sensitive

TCTAAGTGCAAGCACTTGTACTGTGAAACTGCGAATGGCTCATTATATCAGTTATAGTTTAT
TTGATAGATGCCTACTACTTGGATAACCGTAGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCAACAAAG
CCCAACTTTTCGGACGGGCTGTATTTATTAGATAGAAACCAATGCGGGGTTTTCCCCGGT
GTTGTGGTGAGTCATAATAACTAAGCGAATCGCAGTGGCTTCGGCCGGCGATGAATCAT
TCAAGTTTCTGCCCTATCAGCTGTCGATGGTAGGGTATTGGCCTACCATGGCGTTAACGG
GTGA

ASV17|Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Rhips paraornata|Sensitive

TCTAAGAATAAACCGAATATGGTAAATCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCTTAGTTTAT
TGGATCTTGATTCTTACTTGGATAACCGTAGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCACTCAAGC
CCTGACTTCGGAAAGGGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAAGTTGGCCTCGGCCATCTCTC
TGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCAGATCGCACGGTCTCGCACCGGCGACATATCCTTCAA
GTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTAA

ASV18|unassigned|Sensitive

TCTAAGCATGAACTGAATTAAGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTATAACAGCCGTTGTTTC
TTGGATCTCCATTCTTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCTTCAA
GCCCTGCCCTCACGGAACGGGTGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCCGGCGCAAGCCGTT
GTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTGAGCGAATCGCATGGTCTAGCACCAGCGATGTATCTTCA
AGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTAA

ASV20|Enoplida;Thoracostomopsidae;Enoploides sp. |Sensitive

TCTCAGTACATACTGATTAATAGTGAAACCGCAAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCTATAGTTTAT
TAGATCTTACTCTACATGGATACCTGTGGTAACCTAAGAGCTAATACATGCAACAAAGCCC
TATTGCAGGGCGCATTATTAGGACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGCTTATTGGTGGATC
TGAATAACTTTGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGTACTGGCGATGTATCTTTCAAATATCTGCCT
TATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGCTTACACGACTACCATGGTTGTTACGGGTAA

ASV21|Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Chromadorita tentabundum|Sensitive

TCTAAGCATAAGCCGAATATGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTTAT
TGGATCTTAGAGTCCTACTTGGATACCTGTGGAAATCTAGAGCTAATACACGCAATCAA
GCCCCAACCTGACGGACGGGGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATTGGCTTCGGCCATA
AATTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCTGATCGCATGGTCTCGTACCGGCGACGTATCCTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTGATGGTAGTCTATAAGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
A

ASV23|Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Neochromadora sp.|Sensitive

TCTAAGCATAAACCGAATATGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTTAT
TGGATCTTAGAGTCCTACTTGGATACCTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCAATCAAG
CCCCAACCTGACGGGCGGGGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATTGGCTTCGGCCATCT
ATTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCTGATCGCACGGTCTCGCACC GGCGACGTATCCTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
A

ASV32|Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Desmodora pontica|Sensitive

TCTAAGCATGAGCCGAATTATGGTGAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCTTTGTTT
CTTGGATCTTGAATACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCAACCAAGC
TCTGACCTTGGGAAGGAGTGCATTTATTAGACCAAGACCAATCAGGCTTTGCCTGGAA
TCTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTTTGCTGATCACACGGTCTTAGCACC GGCGACATATCTTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGT
AA

ASV35|Desmodorida;Monoposthiidae;Monoposthia mirabilis|Sensitive

TTTAAGCACAAGCCGATAAATGGTGAAGCCGCGGACAGCTCATTAACTCCTAATCC
TAGCAATGCTTACTTTTATGGATATCTGTGCTAATTGTAGAGCTAATACACGCAGAAAAGC
CCAAGATTCTTGGGTGCATTTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTCTGTTGGTG
AATCTGAATAACTGTGCAGATCGCATGGTCCAGTACCGGCGACACATTGCAGGAGTGAG
TGCTTATCAACTTTAGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTATCACGGGTAA

ASV40|Chromadorida;Chromadoridae;Prochromadorella antarctica|Sensitive

TCTAAGCATAAGCCGAATATGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTTAT
TGGATCTGAATATCCTACTTGGATACCTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAAG
CCCTGACCTTACGGGAAGGGCGCATTATTAGAACAAGACCAATTGGCTTCGGCCATTC
ATTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCAGATCGCACGGTCTCGTACCGGCGACATATCCTTCA
AGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTCGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTA
A

ASV44|unassigned|Sensitive

TCTAAGTATAAACACCTTTATACTGTGAAACTGCGAACGGCTCATTATATCAGCAATAATTT
ATTTGATGGTTTCTTACTACATGGATAACTGTAGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCGTAAAA
TCCCAACTCTCGCGGGGAGGGATGTATTTATTAGATAAAAAACCAATGCGGTCTCTGGCC
GGTTTTGTGGTGAATCATAGTAACTTTTCGAATCGCATGGCTTCACGCCGGCGATAGTTC
ATTCAAATTTCTGCCTTATCAGCTTTGACGGTAGTGTAGTGGACTACCGTGGCGTTAAC
GGGTAA

ASV54|Desmodorida;Microlaimidae;Calomicrolaimus parahonestus|Sensitive

TTTAAATACAAGCCTTAAAACGGTGAAATCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATTGTTTC
TTGGATCTTACTTTCTACTTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCATTCAAGT
TCCGACGCAAGAAGGAACGCATTTATTAGAACTAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTTGTTT
GGTGAATCTGAATAACTCCGCAGATCGCATGGTCTAGCACCGGCGACATATCTTTCAAGT
GTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGACTACCATGGTTGTTACGGGTAA

ASV2|Araeolaimida;Comesomatidae;Sabatieria punctata|Tolerant

TCTAAGCAGAAGCCGAACAACGGTAAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTCGTT
TCTTGGATCTCTTATTTTACTTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCACTAAA
GCTCCGACCTTACGGGACGAGCGCATTATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGTTTCGGCCCG
TCCGTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCCGATCGCACGGTCTCGTACCGGCGACATATCT
TTCAAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGG
GTAA

ASV4|unassigned|Tolerant

TCTAAGTATAACAACCTTTATACTGTAAAACCTGCGAACGGCTCATTATATCAGCAATAATTTA
TTTGATGGTACCTTACTACATGGATAACTGTAGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCGTAAAGT
CCCGACTCTTGCGGGGAGGGATGTATTTATTAGATAAAAAACCAATGCGGCTTCGGCCG
GTTTTGTGGTGAATCATAGTAACTTTTCGAATCGCATGGCTTCACGCCGGCGATAGTTCA
TTCAAATTTCTGCCCTATCAGCTTTTCGACGGTAGTGTAGTGGACTACCGTGGCGTTAACG
GGTAA

ASV7|Enoplida;Thoracostomopsidae;Enoploides sp. |Tolerant

TCTCAGTACATACTGATTAATAGTGAAACCGCAAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCTATAGTTTAT
TAGATCTTACTCTACATGGATACCTGTGGTAACCTAAGAGCTAATACATGCAACAAAGCCC
TATTGCAGGGCGCATTTATTAGGACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGCTTATTGGTGGATC
TGAATAACTTTGCTAATCGCACAGTCCTCGTACTGGCGATGTATCTTTCAAATATCTGCCT
TATCAACTGTGATGGTAGCTTACACGACTACCATGGTTGTTACGGGTAA

ASV12|Desmodorida;Desmodoridae;Metachromadora remanei|Tolerant

TCTAAGCATGAGCCGAATTATGGTGAAGCCGCGAATGGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTTGTTT
CTTGGATCTTGATTTACTTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCAACCAAGC
TCCAACCTTTTCGGAAGGAGCGCATTTATTATACCAAGACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGCTATC
TGGTGAATCTGAATAACTTTGCTGATCACATGGTCATAGTACCGGTGACATATCTTTCAAG
TGTCTGCCCTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTATGTGCCTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGTAA

ASV70|Chromadorida;Cyatholaimidae;Praeacanthonus punctatus|Tolerant

TCTAAGCACAAGCCAAAAACGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCATAGTTT
ATTGGATCTTCTCTATACATGGATACCTGCAGTAATTCTGGAGCTAATACACGCAAAAAG
CTCCAACCTTACGGGCGGAGCGCATTTATTAGAACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTGCCCGTAG
TTTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTCAGCTGATCGCACAGTCCTCGCACTGGCGACGTATCTTTC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTGTGATGGTAGTTTACATGACTACCATGGTTGTAACGGGT
AA

ASV75|Monhysterida;Xyalidae;Daptonema oxycerca|Tolerant

TCTAAGCATAAACTAATCTAAAGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCATTACAACAGCCGTTGTTTC
TTGGATCTCCGTCTTACTTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACATGCACACGAGC
TCTAACCTTACGGGAAGAGCGCATTTGATTAGACAAAACCAATCGGGCTTCGGTTCGTTTAC
TTGGTGAATCTGAATAACTACGCAATCGCTTAGGTTTTAAACCGGCGATATGTCCTTCAA
GTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTCGATGGTAGTTTCTGTGACTACCATGGTTGCGACGGGTAA

ASV76|unassigned|Tolerant

TCTCAGCACAAAGCCAAAACAAGGTGAAGCCGCGAATAGCTCAATATAACAGTCATTGTTT
ACTGGATCTTAACCATCCTACTTGGATAACTGTGGTAATTCTAGAGCTAATACACGCAAAA
AGCTCTGACCTTCTGGAATGAGCGCATTATTAGAACAAAACCAATGGGGCTTGCCCCTA
ACTGGTGGATCTAAGTAACTCAGCTGATCGCACGACCTCGTGTGCGGCGACGTATCTTCC
AAGTGTCTGCCTTATCAACTTTTGATGGTAGTTTATGCGACTACCATGGTTGCAACGGGT
AA

